

THE LITERARY HERITAGE OF IBN SINA

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Rezume: This article described with some sources and it about share of the poetry and the book about poetry which is written by great scholar and king of medicine Abu Ali ibn Sino. And also, there are some opinions about Ibn Sino in the article.

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Avicenna is the most famous of all time and peoples
one of the people is a well-known Muslim scholar...!!!
(J. Sarton)

The country of Turkestan is the homeland of famous scientists and thinkers. Scientists who have grown out of this land have not only become mature specialists in their field, but also have done very extensive and effective work in various fields of science, namely, those who have encyclopedic knowledge. Therefore, they were honored to be called the great scientist "thinker". Here is Abu Ali ibn Sina, one of such scholars. Our great-grandfather was described as" the Sultan of Medicine". His scientific heritage in the field of Medicine has been used so far as the main source of World Scientists. "Sheikh ur-rai" (Ibn Sina was called so in the East) is not only a genius of the science of medicine, but also has a much stronger knowledge in the field of philosophy, jurisprudence, logic, mathematics and poetry. Nazarov emphasizes . He also knew the religion and philosophy of Islam perfectly. Ibn Sina's poetry is especially peculiar. It reflects medicine, philosophy

and other sciences in Nazism. Below we see how Avicenna made a magnificent creation in poetry.

The science of Medicine is one of the prominent poets of the Sultan's time. Ibn Sina East is one of the founders of the Rubai genre, especially in Persian poetry. He also wrote continents in Arabic. We can also meet such genres as ghazals, fard, narratives in the work of Ibn Sina. We can take the example of “the story of the time”, “the story of Salomon and Ibsul” and “the story of Hay ibn Yaqzan” among his pre-known stories. Sheikh ur-raisa also wrote a medical work called Urjuza, which explains the issues of medicine with nazm in a popular way. There is also a work on his literary work “The Art of poetry”. This work is the logic part of the book “ash-healing”, which consists of four parts, is the third part. In this book, Ibn Sina covered his views and attitudes to literature. The book "The Art of poetry" consists of eight chapters and they are as follows:

1. General understanding of poetry, about the poetic norm and varieties of Greek poetry.
2. In the poem is a question of theme and imitation.
3. The mood of the poem at the beginning of its appearance and the types of poetry.
4. The relationship of the measure of bytes with the goal-caves, and in particular about the tragedy, the description of the children of tragedy.
5. The poem in particular is about the order of the structure of the tragedy and the sentence fragments inherent in the epos used in it.
6. About the parts of tragedy.
7. The words used in the varieties of poetry and their compatibility are about tragedy and the fact that other types of poems are similar to it.
8. About the poet's shortcomings, and about the advantage of tragedy from similar species.

Through this work, the great thinker fully illuminates the art of poetry. Of course, a person can't reveal such a depth of art that he did not master perfectly.

In the work “Al-Qanun fit-tib”, which is considered the main guide of the healers of the whole world, we also meet poetic fragments . About this work I A Karimov writes in the work "High spirituality is an invincible force" ““the famous scientist, Ibn Sina, who has a unique knowledge, the work of” Medical Law “has served as the fundamental basis of the concepts of” Medicine“,” healthy lifestyle " on a global scale, having studied for several centuries as one of the main medical textbooks in the most prestigious European universities”.

Above we have considered the proof of the fact that the Sultan of Medicine has an unusual and incomparable place in the field of literature, poetry. So, we can say that Ibn Sina is recognized not only as a “great physician”, but also as a talented poet, a great writer. We must perfectly study the glorious creativity of our grandfather, the youth. After all,” to be a generation worthy of Ancestors " is a high duty for every Uzbek child!

Literature:

- 1. A. Irisov the booklet published on the basis of the candidate's dissertation on the story "Salomon va Ibsol" page 19.**
- 2. F. Hasanov “Ma’naviyat yulduzlari” page 88.**
- 3. A. Irisov “Nazmlarda o’gitlar. Ibn Sino she’rlari” page 22.**